

IMPLEMENTATION OF ARABIC LANGUAGE AND ISLAMIC VALUES EDUCATION (ALIVE) IN BALO-I WEST DISTRICT: PERCEPTIONS OF ASATIDZ

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 6

Pages: 786-805

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2391

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13826413

Manuscript Accepted: 06-27-2024

Implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in Balo-I West District: Perceptions of Asatidz

Norhanifa P. Asum, * Carlito A. Abarquez

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the level of implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in Balo-i West District as perceived by the Asatidz. This study utilized descriptive correlation. The study investigated the relationship between the variables presented. This was conducted at Balo-i West District, Division of Lanao del Norte II and 38 Arabic teachers were utilized as participants. The study made use of standardized questionnaires. The data were treated using frequency and percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation, and Pearson Correlation. The study revealed that most of the respondents were 40-49 years of age, female, married, high school graduates in English education, undergraduate level in the Arabic education, passed the qualifying examination for Arabic teachers, and contractual employees. They were teachers for 11-15 years and attended five or more seminars. They displayed high competencies in skills, attitude, and knowledge. They were highly challenged in delayed honorarium. Findings revealed that instructional materials were the most provided and accessible among teachers. The teachers' level of teaching competencies was not significantly associated with their personal profile (except for civil status) and thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the respondents' profile and level of teaching competencies was not rejected. Results showed that the respondent's level of teaching competencies was not significantly associated with the effectiveness of ALIVE implementation. An output was designed based from the findings of the study.

Keywords: *ALIVE, arabic language, islamic values, descriptive-correlational, asatidz*

Introduction

The Arabic Language and Islamic values Education (ALIVE) is a curriculum integrated into the K-12 curriculum of the Department of Education (DepEd) aimed to supplement the needs of Muslim learners not only Muslim-dominated areas but throughout the country.

The integration of ALIVE program in K to 12 BEC could provide Muslim students with the grounds of knowledge especially on Arabic language and values, Islamic belief, and in living with their daily life. Learning the Arabic language strengthen the Muslim student's groundwork of knowledge of Islam religion. The language enables students to attend fellowships and to worship Allah according to

Islam tradition. Learning to communicate using Arabic Language is very useful on

Muslim's life routine and so as in dealing with their brethren in other Muslim community, local and overseas. This language is also the only medium in exploring the wisdom of their religion.

ALIVE program is essential not only in learning the Arabic Language but also in developing their children's reading skills which eventually enable them to read and understand the Qur'an. Learning Arabic and Islamic values at early age would strengthen their hold on participating in the programs and actions for community growth. Equipped with the knowledge obtained from ALIVE program, the students could be exposed to community trust building and delegated with some basic tasks. Early exposure to community building could advance the development of participative behavior.

It has always been the aspiration of every Muslim Filipino to preserve and strengthen the Islamic faith not only in Mindanao but in the entire country. A part of this unrelenting optimism has come into reality when the government reconsiders its policy through the establishment and implementation of related laws providing the teaching of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) both in private and public schools in basic education. However, based on empirical observations, there are pressing concerns in the implementation of ALIVE such as the teaching qualification of Asatidz, lack of instructional materials and relevant training, overpopulated classes, and shortage of classrooms. Most often than not, Asatidz enjoyed instructional freedom and taught with no prepared lesson plans being required of them.

Considering the identified challenges, if not being addressed, these would eventually result in poor classroom management, thus, may forfeit the noble purpose of molding learners into better Islamic practitioners. Despite ALIVE inclusion in the DepEd curriculum, if not properly monitored and supervised, the occurrence of these problems is inevitable. These lead to poor inculcation of Arabic language and Islamic values to learners. With its underlying principle, the ALIVE program serves as an avenue for every Muslim learner to understand the world. And it would serve as a living factor of knowing what is right and what is wrong following Islamic perspectives and its awareness of responsibilities, and the law implemented in the society and the country (Deporos, 2015).

In adherence to the mandate stipulated in Article XIV of the Philippine Constitution, there is a global commitment to Education for

All to provide access to quality education to all children as rights-holders irrespective of their race, color, religion, or culture (Department of Education, 2004). With this, through the issuance of DepEd Order No. 51, s. 2004, the Muslim learners of Mindanao and other parts of the country are provided with an Islamic Education that is authentic and appropriate which is aimed at establishing Islamic schools that would prepare generations of learned and intellectual Muslims imbued with Islamic values and spiritually prepared to serve the people and the country.

Furthermore, the K-12 curriculum in the Philippines strengthened the inclusion of the ALIVE (Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education) program to provide Muslim learners with appropriate and relevant educational opportunities while recognizing their cultural contexts and unique purposes for participating in the program offerings. It also aims to integrate content and competencies which are relevant and of interest to Muslim learners. The program is headed by ALIVE coordinators which include Education Program Supervisors, school heads, and teachers who are designated as coordinators at regional, division, and school levels to oversee and supervise Madrasah Education Program (MEP) implementation (DepEd Order 41, 2017).

Considering the ALIVE program as an integral part of the educative process, there is a dire need to effectively implement it for the realization of its aims which are aligned with DepEd's vision. However, in the context of the district where the study will be conducted, observation reveals that there are several Asatidz who lack the skills on teaching the primary and intermediate learners since they do not have enough educational backgrounds to meet the needs of providing quality education as the main objective of the program based on the guidelines. According to McKinsey (2007), the quality of the educational system does not exceed the quality of its teachers. Undeniably, if DepEd will not give a lens on how the underlying concerns are addressed through monitoring and evaluating its implementation, these would remain one of the serious obstacles to the realization of its vision. With the observations and contentions, as a public-school teacher whose learners are part of the ALIVE program and a devoted Muslima who has the earnest aspiration to preserve the teaching of Islam to the younger generation, the researcher would like to delve into the implementation of ALIVE in Balo-i West District through unveiling the perceptions of the Asatidz for School Year 2020-2021. This study hopes to formulate an action plan to address the challenges and difficulties they have encountered.

Research Questions

This study investigated the level of implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in Balo-i West District as perceived by the Asatidz. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of,
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment in;
 - 1.3.1 secular education;
 - 1.3.2 Madrasah education;
 - 1.4 eligibility;
 - 1.5 appointment status;
 - 1.6 number of years in teaching;
 - 1.7 number of trainings attended related to teaching and Madrasah Education; and
 - 1.8 monthly salary/honorarium?
2. What is the level of respondents' teaching competencies in terms of
 - 2.1 knowledge;
 - 2.2 skills; and
 - 2.3 attitude?
3. What are the challenges encountered by the respondents in teaching ALIVE?
4. What is the level of effectiveness of ALIVE implementation as perceived by the respondents in terms of
 - 4.1 availability of school facilities;
 - 4.2 availability of instructional materials; and
 - 4.3 the extent of instructional support?
5. What is the annual teaching performance of the Asatidz?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their level of teaching competencies?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of teaching competencies and the effectiveness of ALIVE implementation?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the socio-demographic & annual teaching performance of the Asatidz?
9. What action plan can be formulated based on the output of the study?

Methodology

This section presents the research design, research environment, the respondents and sampling procedure, the research instrument and its validity, the data gathering procedure, and the statistical treatment of the data.

Research Design

Descriptive-correlational design was used to assess the level of implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in Balo-i West District as perceived by the Asatidz. Specifically, the study delved into the demographic profile of the Asatidz to be correlated with their level of teaching competence as to knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Determining their challenges encountered in teaching ALIVE was also included.

Furthermore, it also assessed the level of effectiveness of ALIVE implementation in terms of the availability of school facilities and instructional materials, and the extent of instructional support provided to the Asatidz. This correlated with their level of teaching competence.

Participants

The study purposively included the entire population of thirty-eight (38) Asatidz from the Balo-i West District as respondents. Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents Per School*

<i>Name of Schools (Balo-i West District)</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total Number of ALIVE Teachers</i>
1. Balo-i Central ES	6	10	16
2. Momungan ES	1	3	4
3. Pacalundo ES	2	2	4
4. Matampay ES	0	2	2
5. Dadoan ES	0	1	1
6. Bangko ES	1	1	2
7. Olango ES	1	1	2
8. Basagad ES	0	1	1
9. Balut ES	0	1	1
10. Bulao PS	0	1	1
11. Mamaanun PS	0	1	1
12. Patpangkat PS	0	1	1
13. Bubong a Paco PS	0	1	1
14. Maliwanag PS	0	1	1
Overall			38

Instruments

The study made use of a survey questionnaire and interview as a backup about their challenges as an ASATIDZ in gathering data. It was adapted from Solaiman's (2017) on his research entitled "Implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in Marawi City, Philippines: Unveiling the Perceptions of ALIVE Teachers."

The first part of the questionnaire gauged the demographic profile of the Asatidz in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, eligibility, appointment status, number of years in teaching, number of trainings attended, and monthly salary/honorarium.

The second part consisted of items that determined their level of teaching competence in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. It also included the challenges they encountered in teaching ALIVE.

Lastly, the third part identified the level of effectiveness of ALIVE implementation as to the availability of school facilities, availability of instructional materials, and extent of instructional support. The questionnaire was written in English and was subjected to approval from the thesis adviser and panel members before its distribution.

Procedure

According to O'leary (2004), well-documented and systematic data gathering was essential to generate a more credible conclusion in any research. Thus, the researcher carefully devised a systematic data gathering to be able to obtain reliable results. The researcher strictly followed the entry protocol of the Department of Education. The researcher secured permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Lanao del Norte through a letter of request duly signed by the Dean of the Graduate School of St. Peters College for the conduct of the study. Secondly, after the permissions were granted, the researcher sought permission from the school heads of the schools under the Balo-i West District. The researcher also personally distributed the questionnaires to the respondents, and They gathered in a certain area for further instruction and clarification regarding the questions of the study.

Observance of the ethical standards of research was done in the data gathering. The researcher also gave a letter of consent to the respondents requesting them to participate in the study. Before the distribution of the said questionnaire, the respondents were informed of what the research was all about. They were also given the freedom to participate or decline to participate as respondents. They were asked to sign to manifest their will to take part in this research. They were also assured that their identity and answers would be

kept confidential, and their responses would not be disclosed.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data.

For problem 1, Frequency and Percentage Distribution were used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, eligibility, appointment status, number of years in teaching, and number of trainings attended related to teaching, and Madrasah Education, and monthly salary.

For problems 2, 3, 4, and 5, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the (1) level of Asatidz's teaching competencies in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitude and (2) the level of effectiveness of ALIVE implementation in terms of availability of school facilities, availability of instructional materials, and extent of instructional support.

For problems 6, 7, and 8, Pearson-r Correlation was utilized to determine the significant relationship among variables.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered by the researcher as well as the analysis and interpretation.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment in secular education and Madrasah education, eligibility, appointment status, number of years in teaching, number of trainings attended related to teaching and Madrasah Education, and monthly salary/honorarium?

Table 2. Age of the Respondents

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean \pm SD
20-29	6	15.8	
30-39	11	28.9	
40-49	13	34.2	40.63 \pm 9.89
50-59	8	21.1	
Total	38	100.0	

Figure 1. Age Profile

Table 2 (Figure 1) presents the age profile of the respondents. Results showed that 13 or 34.2% of the total respondents belonged to 40-49 years of age, 11 or 28.9% of them were having 30-39 years of age, 8 or 21.1% of them were 50-59 years of age, and 6 or 15.8% of them were 20-29 years of age. The mean age of the respondents was 40.63 years with the variability of 9.89 years. It was a common observation that age influenced teaching because it was associated with no experience (Bodhe et al., 2015). This was because as the age advanced, teachers became experienced, and they knew where to tap the potential of the students and how to make them understand their worth.

Table 3. Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	13	34.2
Female	25	65.8
Total	38	100.0

Figure 2. Sex Profile

Table 3 (Figure 2) presents the sex profile of the respondents. Results described that 25 or 65.8% of the total respondents were female while 13 or 34.2% were male. This implied that there were more female Asatidz than the males which meant that more female Arabic teachers were involved in the teaching profession. In a recent study by Shah et al. (2018), they found that students were little toward biased to female teachers, which may be a related to variety of factors like empathic listening, better, understanding, and view of concern shown by them.

Table 4. Civil Status of the Respondents

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	7	18.4
Married	23	60.5
Widow	7	18.4
Separated	1	2.6
Total	38	100.0

Figure 3. Civil Status Profile

Table 4 (Figure 4) presents the civil status profile of the respondents. Results showed that 23 or 60.5 were married, 7 or 18.4 % were single, 7 or 18.4% were widows, and 1 or 2.6% were separated. This implied that most of the Arabic teachers were married. The study carried out by Khurshid, Qasmi, and As-huraf (2012), found that marital status affected the self-efficacy of teachers and that married male and female teachers had high self-efficacy which led to high job performance.

Table 5. Educational Attainment in Secular Education of the Respondents

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Elementary	6	15.8
High School	18	47.4
Undergraduate	13	34.2
Graduate degree	1	2.6
Graduate degree (ongoing)	0	0.0
Total	38	100.0

Figure 4. *Secular Education Profile*

Table 5 (Figure 4) presents the education profile of the respondents. Results showed that 18 or 47.4% of the total respondents were high school graduates, 13 or 34.2% were undergraduates, 6 or 15.8% were elementary graduates, and 1 or 2.6% finished a graduate degree in Arabic education. The results implied that most of the respondents were high school graduates followed by respondents with baccalaureate degree included in the study were equipped with educational qualifications that can support their Arabic teaching. According to Ponders (2011), teachers’ educational attainment was correlational to their teaching skills and performance. He observed that the more teachers sought for educational growth the more they became equipped with the necessary teaching methodologies to employ in actual teaching.

Table 6. *Educational Attainment in Madrasa Education of the Respondents*

Madrasa Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Elementary	0	0.0
High School	15	39.5
Undergraduate	17	44.7
Graduate degree	5	13.2
Graduate degree (ongoing)	1	2.6
Total	38	100.0

Figure 5. *Madrasa Education Profile*

Table 6 (Figure 5) presents the Madrasah education profile of the respondents. Results showed that 17 or 44.7% were undergraduate level, 15 or 39.5% were high school completers, 5 or 13.2 were graduate degree completers, and 2.6% had an ongoing graduate degree. This meant that the majority of the respondents had a degree in Arabic education which implied that the respondents were qualified in terms of Arabic education.

Table 7. *Eligibility of the Respondents*

Eligibility	Frequency	Percentage (%)
LET Passer	5	13.2
PBET Passer	0	0.0
CSC	0	0.0
QEALIS	33	86.8
Total	38	100.00

Figure 6. Eligibility Profile

Table 7 (Figure 6) presents the eligibility of the respondents. As revealed, 33 or 86.8% passed the qualifying examination for Arabic teachers while 5 or 13.2% were LET passers. These LET passers were allowed to be accepted as contractual Asatidz while waiting for permanent position in DepEd.

Table 8. Appointment Status of the Respondents

Appointment Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Permanent	2	5.3
Contractual	36	94.7
Total	38	100.0

Figure 7. Appointment Status Profile

Table 8 (Figure 7) presents the appointment status of the respondents. As revealed, 36 or 94.7% were contractual and 2 or 5.3% were permanent. This revealed that the majority of the Arabic teachers were giving services on a contractual basis. According to Omoifo et al., (2010), appointment status or working status of a teachers found out that they more strive harder to achieve a permanent status which meant they continuously improved their mode of instruction and their work ethics.

Table 9. Years of Service of the Respondents

Years of Service	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-5	10	26.3
6-10	13	34.2
11-15	13	34.2
16-21 above	2	5.3
Total	38	100.0

Table 9 (Figure 8) presents the years of service of the respondents. As revealed, 13 or 34.2% were teachers for 11-15 years, while 13 or 34.2% were teachers for 6-10 years, 10 or 26.3% were teachers for 1-5 years, and 2 or 5.3% were teachers 21 and above. According to Biyani et al. (2013), teaching experience was positively associated with student achievement gains throughout a teacher's career. Gains in teacher effectiveness associated with experience were most steep in teachers' initial years but continue to be significant as teachers reach the second, and often third, decades of their careers.

Figure 8. Years of Service Profile

Table 10. Number of Seminars Attended by the Respondents

Number of Seminar Attended	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 – 3	11	29.0
4 – 5	6	15.8
Above 5	21	55.3
Total	38	100.0

Figure 9. Seminar Attended Profile

Table 10 (Figure 9) presents the seminar attended profile of the respondents. As revealed, 21 or 55.3% attended the above five seminars, 11 or 29% attended 1-3 seminars, and 6 or 15.8% attended 4 to 5 seminars. This implied that more than half of the respondents attended a good number of seminars related to Arabic teaching which meant that they continuously sought for professional growth. According to Biryani et al. (2013), teachers’ attendance in these seminars would help create an effective learning environment, improve teaching-learning situations, keep updated on modern instructional devices, and inspire them to become better teachers in the modern world.

Table 11. Monthly Honorarium of the Respondents

Monthly Salary or Honorarium	Frequency	Percentage (%)
500.00 – 700.00	0	0.0
900.00 – 1,500.00	0	0.0
2,000.00 – 3,000.00	10	26.3
4,000.00 – 5,000.00	28	73.7
Total	38	100.0

Table 11 (Figure 10) presents the monthly salary of the respondents. As revealed, 28 or 73.7% had a monthly salary of 4000-5000 while 10 or 26.3% had a monthly salary of 2000-3000. This 2000-3000, they were new in contract, and they were hired 5 years below. On the other hand, the 28 Asatidz received 40005000 honorariums because they were 4-5 years long in service. They received honorarium from the school division through their ATM cards and it is usually delayed every 2-3 months.

In these past years, the LGU gave them small amount of honorarium but for now, they don’t get any allowances from them. But in other municipalities, they still provide honorarium for their Asatidz. As mentioned by Subroto (2013), increasing the amount of income received by teachers such as salaries, subsidies, honorarium, and other income brought a significant effect on improving their quality of teaching.

Figure 10. Monthly Honorarium Profile

Problem 2: What is the level of respondents’ teaching competencies in terms of knowledge, skills, and attitude?

Table 12 (Figure 12) presents the level of respondents teaching competencies in terms of knowledge. The result reflected that the teachers had a high level of knowledge in their teaching competencies (M=2.87, SD=0.46). The teachers perceived had high knowledge level of the topic they were discussing (M=3.05, SD=0.61), they were well prepared for their lesson (M=2.95, SD=0.73,) and applied a range of successful strategies that maintained learning environments that motivated their learners (M=2.92, SD=0.75). Thus, the teachers manifested a high knowledge level of teaching competencies.

It can be analyzed based on the results of the study that the Asatidz manifested a high knowledge level which meant that they possessed high competency in teaching their fields of discipline. This also meant that implementation of Arabic education among schools would be easier because the Asatidz were equipped with desirable knowledge they could impart to their students.

Table 12. Level of Respondents’ Teaching Competencies in Terms of Knowledge

Indicators	Mean ± SD	Description
K1. I have sufficient knowledge of the topic I am discussing.	3.05±0.61	High
K2. I have adequate training in his/her field of discipline.	2.55±0.69	High
K3. I use knowledge and principles of teaching and learning to enhance professional practice.	2.89±0.83	High
K4. I am well prepared for my lesson.	2.95±0.73	High
K5. I apply a range of successful strategies that maintain learning environments that motivate learners.	2.92±0.75	High
Total Measure	2.87±0.46	High

Note: 1.00-1.49 Low; 2.50-3.49 High; 1.50-2.49 Moderate; 3.50-4.00 Very High

Figure 11. Knowledge Level

According to Kiamba et al. (2017), teachers’ intellectual resources and dispositions largely determined their capacity to engage

students’ minds and hearts in the learning process. Teachers’ subject matter knowledge may be affected by the attitudes and expectations that their students brought to the classroom. Teachers’ understanding of subject matter affected their capacity to simplify content to help students to understand. Ademulegun (2011) added that students taught by teachers who were more qualified and experienced in terms of the subject matter performed better than those taught by far less qualified and experienced teachers.

Table 13. Level of Respondents’ Teaching Competencies in Terms of Attitude

Indicators	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. An ALIVE teacher has commitment and dedication to his/her assigned task.	3.05 \pm 0.57	Agree
2. An ALIVE teacher must have loyalty to her/his institution.	2.97 \pm 0.72	Agree
3. An ALIVE teacher is willing to serve even with less remuneration and is an epitome of compassion.	3.05 \pm 0.87	Agree
4. An ALIVE teacher is willing to give services despite bad weather and is not in good working conditions.	3.03 \pm 0.59	Agree
5. An ALIVE teacher is willing to extend extra effort to provide good services to learners who need special attention.	2.89 \pm 0.73	Agree
Total Measure	3.00 \pm 0.40	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 Low; 2.50-3.49 High; 1.50-2.49 Moderate; 3.50-4.00 Very High

Figure 12. Attitude Level

Table 13 (Figure 12) presents the level of respondents’ teaching competencies in terms of attitudes. The result reflected that teacher had a high level of positive attitudes in their teaching competencies (M=3.00, SD=0.40). The teachers displayed high attitudes in their field of expertise because they had commitment and dedication to their assigned tasks (M=3.05, SD=0.57). They were willing to serve even less remuneration and an epitome of compassion (M=3.05, SD=0.87), they were willing to give services despite their working conditions (M=3.03, SD=0.59), they had loyalty to their institution (M=2.97, SD=0.72), and they were willing to extend extra effort to provide good services to learners who needed special attention (M=2.89, SD=0.73).

It can be analyzed based on the results of the study that the Asatidz teachers manifested a positive attitude which meant that they possessed high competency in teaching their fields of discipline. This also meant that implementation of Arabic education among schools would be easier because the Asatidz were equipped to display attitudes necessary to perform their roles and responsibilities well. According to Kimosop (2015), teachers’ attitudes towards teaching influence the success of any learning program implementation. A classroom is a place where children flock to learn new things, and it can be a bit crazy sometimes. Teachers displayed positivity and strong-willed personalities influenced students’ attitudes toward learning as well.

Additionally, teachers’ attitudes were displayed by their manifested commitments. According to Brit et al. (2018), professional commitment refers to an attitude that someone has towards her job and the teaching profession. A committed teacher must possess certain qualities to perform her functions efficiently and effectively. Teachers who displayed positive attitudes were also found to have a strong loyalty to their profession (Fako et al., 2018). The implementation of Arabic learning was believed to be more of a success if the qualified teachers showed strong commitment and loyalty that would help them overcome any challenges.

Table 14. Level of Respondents’ Teaching Competencies in Terms of Skills

Indicators	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. I am a good facilitator of learning.	2.92 \pm 0.59	High
2. An ALIVE teacher is a good repository of materials for learning or a	3.05 \pm 0.77	High

librarian.		
3. I have sound classroom management skills.	2.97±0.59	High
4. I am a good communicator of ideas.	2.89±0.65	High
5. I possess the ability to listen to students' needs.	3.18±0.56	High
Total Measure	3.01 ± 0.40	High

Note: 1.00-1.49 Low; 2.50-3.49 High; 1.50-2.49 Moderate; 3.50-4.00 Very High

Figure 13. Skills Level

Table 14 (Figure 13) presents the level of respondents' teaching competencies in terms of skills. The result reflected that teacher had a high level of skills in their teaching competencies (M=3.01, SD=0.40). The teachers displayed high skills in their field of expertise because they believed that they possessed the ability to listen to students' needs (M=3.18, SD=0.56), they can be a source of learning materials (M=3.05, SD=0.77), they had sound classroom management (M=2.97, SD=0.59), they were good facilitators of learning (M=2.92, SD=0.59), and they were a good communicator of ideas (M=2.89, SD=0.65). It can be analyzed based on the results of the study that the Asatidz teachers manifested a high skill in teaching their field. They perceived themselves to be equipped with enough skills to manage, learn, and build good communication with their students.

Acala et al. (2021) stated that teachers were expected to use a wide variety of methods, tools, and approaches and tailor them to the learners' needs. They also needed to have the competences and skills necessary to create a positive classroom environment and work collaboratively with other stakeholders within and outside the school in order to provide timely support to learners. In the implementation of any learning program, teaching skills were crucial when working as an educator. These skills were what help a teacher keep their classroom engaged and interested in learning. Knowing the most desirable teaching skills, as well as how they can highlight them can help find their teaching jobs more enjoyable and fulfilling (Jennings et al., 2010).

Table 15. Consolidated Findings of the Level of Respondents' Teaching Competencies

Teaching Competencies	Mean ± SD	Description
Knowledge	2.87±0.46	High
Attitude	3.00±0.40	High/Agree
Skills	3.01±0.40	High

Note: 1.00-1.49 Low; 2.50-3.49 High; 1.50-2.49 Moderate; 3.50-4.00 Very High

Figure 14. Level of Teaching Competencies

Table 15 (Figure 14) presents the consolidated findings of the level of respondents' teaching competencies in terms of knowledge,

attitude, and skills in teaching. Results revealed that teachers generally manifested a high level of competencies on the three indicators ($M=2.96$, $SD=0.26$). As reflected, they displayed high competencies in skills ($M=3.01$, $SD=0.40$), attitude ($M=3.00$, $SD=0.40$), and knowledge ($M=2.87$, $SD=0.46$). The existence of good skills in interacting with students can support the success of the learning process. Innovation in learning will give new shades to students, will lead to creativity in learning, and will eliminate oversaturated learning (Dahar, 2011).

Problem 3: What are the challenges encountered by the respondents in teaching ALIVE?

Table 16. *Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in Teaching ALIVE*

<i>Challenges Encountered in Teaching ALIVE</i>	<i>Mean \pm SD</i>	<i>Rank</i>
C1. Delayed Salary/Honorarium	2.84 \pm 2.49	2
C2. Lack of Support from Local Government Units	2.66 \pm 1.86	1
C3. Scarce and Limited books	5.84 \pm 2.86	8
C4. Lack of classroom supplies and instructional materials in the teaching of ALIVE	5.42 \pm 2.13	5
C5. Insufficient salaries/allowances provided by the Government	4.42 \pm 1.99	3
C6. Lack of training/seminars in the teaching of ALIVE	5.55 \pm 1.54	6.5
C7. Lack of qualified ALIVE teachers	5.55 \pm 1.77	6.5
C8. Lack of supervision from the DepEd	4.89 \pm 2.18	4

Figure 15. *Challenges Encountered*

Table 16 (Figure 15) presents the challenges encountered by the teachers in teaching ALIVE. Results revealed that lack of support from local government units ranked 1st ($M=2.66$, $SD=1.86$), delayed honorarium ($M=2.84$, $SD=2.49$), insufficient salaries or allowances provided by the government ($M=4.42$, $SD=1.99$), lack of supervision from DepEd ($M=4.89$, $SD=2.18$), lack of classroom supplies and instructional materials in teaching ALIVE ($M=5.42$, $SD=2.13$), lack of training and seminars in teaching ALIVE ($M=5.55$, $SD=1.54$), lack of qualified ALIVE teachers ($M=5.55$, $SD=1.77$), and scarce and limited materials ($M=5.84$, $SD=2.86$).

Based on the interview, the respondents narrated the reason why these three were the highest challenges they encountered as an asatidz:

“Our honorarium was usually delayed every 2-3 months”. Respondent 10

Moreover, almost all schools have a few numbers of Asatidz but still they experienced a lack of support from their LGU.

“In previous school years, we can still receive a support from our LGUs but now they do not provide us anymore” (Respondent 26).

Supplemental learning materials are also needed aside from the traditional books being used in the ALIVE subjects. According to Respondent 2:

“Supplemental reading materials should be considered aside from the traditional books.”

It can be analyzed that among the indicators, lack of support from local government units was found to be highly challenging for the respondents as well as delayed honorariums and insufficient allowances. This implied how financial constraints highly influenced the respondents in many ways. Lack of support from government units near their school and insufficient allowances may hinder their motivation to go to work or perform their duties well because they lack financial means and support.

Support from external sectors was found to increase teachers’ motivation and efficiency (Dangle et al., 2020). Basic public education is still largely the responsibility of the central government, delivered through the Department of

Education (DepEd), notwithstanding the devolution of many basic services to LGUs. However, the local government units (LGUs) do

provide supplementary funding support to public basic education because they had access to a sustainable source of financial resources that were earmarked for the basic education sub-sector, the Special Education Fund (SEF).

The resources that LGUs provided to the basic education sector from their General Fund were quite significant at 7% of total general government spending on basic education from 2001-to 2008. Thus, the LGUs were considered major partners of the national government in the delivery of basic education services.

Accordingly, low salaries granted to teachers of course unable to fulfill the needs of teachers daily, especially for teachers who were married and had children who entered school age (Dahar, 2011). Accordingly, he added that allowances expressed appreciation for teachers. Teachers who are given decent allowances will be able to meet every need and will not neglect to do their duties.

Problem 4: What is the level of effectiveness of ALIVE implementation as perceived by the respondents in terms of availability of school facilities, availability of instructional materials, and the extent of instructional support

Table 17. Level of Effectiveness of ALIVE Implementation in Terms of Availability of School Facilities

Indicators	Mean ± SD	Description
ASF1. The ALIVE rooms are conducive to learning	3.32±0.62	Agree
ASF2. The ALIVE rooms have enough chairs for all learners	3.16±0.82	Agree
ASF3. The ALIVE rooms are well equipped with devices, reading materials, etc.	2.34±0.81	Disagree
ASF4. The ALIVE rooms have good ventilation.	2.89±0.73	Agree
ASF5. The ALIVE rooms have their own comfort rooms for male and female learners.	2.03±0.97	Disagree
Total Measure	2.75±0.45	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 Low; 2.50-3.49 High; 1.50-2.49 Moderate; 3.50-4.00 Very High

Figure 16. Availability of School Facilities

Table 17 (Figure 17) presents the level of effectiveness of ALIVE implementation as perceived by the respondents in terms of the availability of school facilities. Results revealed that the teachers agreed that the ALIVE rooms were conducive to learning (M=3.32, SD=0.62), had enough chairs for all learners (M=3.16, SD=0.8 and 2), and had good ventilation (M=2.89, SD=0.73). However, they disagreed that the ALIVE classrooms were well-equipped with devices, reading materials and etc. (M=2.34, SD=0.81), and had their own comfort rooms for male and female learners (M=2.03, SD=0.97).

It can be analyzed that teachers observed that in terms of school facilities, they received a high amount of support to have their classrooms conducive for learning with enough chairs to accommodate their students. Apparently, the only problem was the unavailability of modern teaching resources and reading materials which were significant to learning. The challenge of having adequate and responsive school facilities had always been one of the primary concerns of every educator since studies had shown that school facilities were the space for interpretation and physical expression of the curricula (Johnson et al., 2016). Therefore, every school must have adequate and functional facilities which can equate to having a relevant and efficient curriculum. Additionally, Lewallen (2016) found that when facilities were present, students were exposed to a variety of activities that somehow motivated students in their learning process. The teachers become challenged too to make use of the school facilities in transferring knowledge to their students, thus making them more effective as educators.

Table 18. Level of Effectiveness of ALIVE Implementation in terms of Availability of Instructional Materials

Indicators	Mean ± SD	Description
AIM1. mThere are enough Learner’s Materials available on teaching ALIVE.	3.00±0.66	Agree

AIM2. There are enough Teacher Guides and Teacher	2.87±0.78	Agree
AIM3. The ALIVE teachers are using the traditional method of teaching e.g. chalk and blackboard.	3.29±0.65	Agree
AIM4. The ALIVE teachers use instructional materials and visual aids in teaching.	3.13±0.74	Agree
AIM5. There is the availability of ICT equipment in teaching ALIVE.	2.58±1.06	Agree
Total Measure	2.97±0.45	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 Low; 2.50-3.49 High; 1.50-2.49 Moderate; 3.50-4.00 Very High

Figure 17. Availability of Instructional Materials

Table 18 (Figure 17) presents the level of effectiveness of ALIVE implementation as perceived by the respondents in terms of the availability of instructional materials. Results revealed that the teachers agreed that they were using the traditional method of teaching (M=3.29, SD=0.74), used instructional materials and visual aids (M=3.13, SD=0.74), there were enough learners’ materials available on teaching the subject (M=3.00, SD=0.66), there were enough teacher guides and teaching materials in the subject (M=2.87, SD=0.78), and there was the availability of ICT equipment in teaching ALIVE (M=2.58, SD=1.06).

It can be analyzed that ALIVE teachers provided instructional materials on their own. Since not all classrooms were ICT equipped, they used the traditional way of teaching. They also incorporated visual aids to make their teaching more engaging. They also believed that there were enough teacher guides and materials they could provide for students.

According to the study by Figueroa, Lim, and Lee (2016), teaching program implementations become more successful with the presence of modernized classrooms. However, in the Philippines, the insufficiency and inadequacy of the necessary school facilities was a perennial national problem but was understudied due to the scarcity of available data on education facilities. As an example, there were some schools in the country with aging school buildings and inadequate school facilities.

It also resembled the study of Jamaluddin and Cadir (2017) in which the financial aspect of the Madrasah was the primary concern for the sustainability of the school, which emanated from the lack of ALIVE teachers and learning resources, and minimal faculty development.

Table 19. Level of Effectiveness of ALIVE Implementation in Terms of Extent of Instructional Support

Indicators	Mean ± SD	Description
EIS1. There is enough support from LGU that is provided to the ALIVE program.	2.16±0.72	Disagree
EIS2. There is regular instructional supervision to ALIVE teaching given by the school head and ALIVE supervisor.	2.87±0.91	Agree
EIS3. There is a regular upgrading of ALIVE materials e.g. textbooks and other references.	3.05±0.52	Agree
EIS4. Our school head talks to teachers about supervision of school and classroom instruction.	3.13±0.58	Agree
EIS5. When we meet after supervision, my school head gives me sufficient time to discuss my difficulties and share my experiences.	3.21±0.66	Agree
Total Measure	2.88±0.33	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 Low; 2.50-3.49 High; 1.50-2.49 Moderate; 3.50-4.00 Very High

Table 19 (Figure 18) presents the level of effectiveness of ALIVE implementation as perceived by the respondents in terms of instructional support. Results revealed that the teachers agreed that their school heads gave them time to discuss their difficulties and experiences (M=3.21, SD=0.66), their school heads talked to them about supervision of school and classroom instruction (M=3.13, SD=0.58), there was a regular upgrading of ALIVE materials such as textbooks and other references (M=3.05, SD=0.52), there was regular instructional supervision (M=2.87, SD=0.91). However, they disagreed that there was enough support from LGU that was provided to the ALIVE program (M=2.16, SD=0.72).

It can be analyzed that ALIVE teachers received instructional supervision from their school heads. This meant that they could constantly voice out their individual difficulties and challenges. They were also supported in terms of providing instructional materials. The

school head’s support was very important among teachers. An instructional leader developed and communicated a vision and goals for his/her school. They should set high standards for student achievement. They should encourage them to improve their teaching practice continuously. Meanwhile, principals who were also instructional leaders positively affected student learning (Hamsira et al., 2022).

Figure 18. Extent of Instructional Support

Additionally, the study by Marasigan (2019) expressed that the Madrasah education in the Philippines had no guidelines for the monitoring of qualified teachers. Further, school heads suggested that annual training and seminars on the construction of summative and formative assessments for the ALIVE program should be part of the program implementation strategy of the teachers. These would help them develop the skills they needed.

Table 20. Consolidated Findings of the Level of Effectiveness of ALIVE Implementation

ALIVE Implementation	Mean ± SD	Description
Availability of School Facilities	2.75±0.45	Agree
Availability of Instructional Materials	2.97±0.45	Agree
Extent of Instructional Support	2.88±0.33	Agree
Total Measure	2.87±0.27	Agree

Figure 19. Effectiveness of ALIVE Implementation

Table 20 presents the consolidated findings of the level of effectiveness of ALIVE implementation. Results revealed that in terms of the implementation of the program, teachers mostly agreed on the availability of instructional materials (M=2.97, SD=0.46), the extent of instructional support (M=2.88, SD=0.33), and the availability of school facilities (M=2.75, M=0.45). This implied that instructional materials were the most provided and accessible among teachers. It can be analyzed that enough support instructional materials, instructional support, and school facilities were provided among the teachers.

The overall finding supported the study of Kuuskorpi and Gonzalez (2011) that if a school provided a quality environment for teachers and students, this would facilitate the acquisition of skills that were necessary for society. Additionally, Lawrence (2012) also emphasized that the school should provide the necessary stimulus to make the learning process meaningful.

Moreover, according to Hamsara et al. (2022), there was a need to contextualize the learning materials to be used in ALIVE subjects. Textbooks were in the Arabic language which must be translated to Maranao and other mother tongue languages of the learners for better understanding. Development and reproduction of big books and other reading materials were emphasized.

Problem 5: What is the annual teaching performance of the Asatidz?

Table 21. Annual Teaching Performance of the Asatidz

Teaching Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Satisfactory	35	92.1
Satisfactory	3	7.9
Total	38	100.0

Figure 20. Annual Teaching Performance Level

Table 21 (Figure 21) displays the Annual teaching performance level of the respondents in the school year 2020-2021. The results indicated 35 or 92.1%, which were most of the newly hired teachers, had a very satisfactory teaching performance rating even during this time of the pandemic. 3 or 7.9% of them, on the other hand, acquired a satisfactory teaching performance rating. This further implied that, even at the pandemic, Asatidz could still produce a satisfactory performance even if different challenges were being thrown at them.

Problem 6: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents’ profile and their level of teaching competencies?

Table 22 presents the relationship between the respondents’ profiles and the level of teaching competencies using Point-Biserial Correlation analysis. Results revealed that the respondents having a single status ($r=-0.387$, $p=0.017$) and married status ($r=0.365$, $p=0.024$) were significantly associated to their perceived level of teaching competencies. Single teachers had lower teaching competencies levels as compared to non-single teachers (married or widowed) and married teachers had higher competencies levels compared to non-married (single and widowed) teachers. However, no statistical relationship was found between the level of teaching competencies and the teachers’ personal profile relative to age, sex, secular education, madrasah education, eligibility, appointment status, years of service, seminar attended, and salary since the corresponding p-values exceeded at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 22. Relationship Between the Respondent’s Profile and Level of Teaching Competencies

Profile	Level of Teaching Competencies			Total Measure
	Knowledge	Attitude	Skills	
Age	0.178 (0.284)	0.108 (0.519)	0.228 (0.169)	0.280 (0.088)
Sex (Female)	0.334* (0.040)	0.000 (1.000)	0.066 (0.696)	0.234 (0.157)
Civil Status				
Single	-0.373* (0.021)	-0.206 (0.214)	-0.109 (0.514)	-0.387* (0.017)
Married	0.248 (0.134)	0.300 (0.067)	0.119 (0.475)	0.365* (0.024)
Widow	0.102 (0.544)	-0.172 (0.302)	-0.006 (0.970)	-0.031 (0.852)
Secular Education				
Elementary	0.340* (0.037)	-0.219 (0.302)	0.286 (0.082)	0.239 (0.149)
High School	-0.222 (0.181)	0.214 (0.198)	-0.305 (0.062)	-0.181 (0.278)
Undergraduate	0.029 (0.861)	-0.056 (0.737)	0.159 (0.342)	0.071 (0.673)
Madrasa Education				
High School	-0.201 (0.227)	-0.055 (0.745)	-0.174 (0.296)	-0.238 (0.150)
Undergraduate	0.156 (0.350)	-0.027 (0.873)	0.175 (0.293)	0.170 (0.307)
Graduate	0.056 (0.736)	0.110 (0.512)	-0.006 (0.973)	0.087 (0.602)
Eligibility (QEALIS)	-0.107 (0.521)	0.039 (0.814)	-0.113 (0.500)	-0.102 (0.541)
Appointment Status (Contractual)	-0.477* (0.002)	-0.119 (0.475)	0.063 (0.709)	-0.315 (0.054)
Years of Service				
1-5	-0.018 (0.915)	-0.242 (0.143)	0.113 (0.500)	-0.077 (0.644)

6-10	0.054 (0.749)	0.253 (0.125)	-0.318 (0.052)	-0.002 (0.991)
11-above	-0.036 (0.830)	-0.027 (0.871)	0.207 (0.213)	0.072 (0.669)
Seminar Attended				
1-3	0.202 (0.225)	-0.235 (0.155)	-0.008 (0.960)	-0.005 (0.975)
4-5	-0.038 (.820)	0.110 (0.512)	-0.079 (0.639)	-0.007 (0.967)
above 5	-0.156 (0.350)	0.134 (0.422)	0.065 (0.696)	0.010 (0.953)
Salary (4000-5000)	0.018 (0.915)	0.242 (0.143)	-0.083 (0.622)	0.093 (0.579)

Specifically, the teachers’ knowledge level of competencies was significantly related to their sex ($r=0.334, p=0.040$), single status ($r=-0.373, p=0.021$), elementary secular education ($r=0.340, p=0.037$) and appointment status ($r=-0.477, p=0.002$). Female teachers had higher knowledge levels compared to male teachers. Single teachers had lower knowledge levels compared to non-single teachers (married or widowed). Further, the teachers who had elementary secular education had significantly more knowledge levels as compared to those teachers who obtained higher secular education. Lastly, the contractual teachers had significantly lower knowledge levels of teaching competencies as compared to regular teachers.

In totality, the teachers’ level of teaching competencies was not significantly associated with their personal profile (except for civil status) and thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the respondents’ profile and level of teaching competencies was not rejected.

According to Shah et al. (2018), there had been a significant relationship between the marital status of teachers and their teaching skills. Their study showed that there was an association between marital dissatisfaction and job dissatisfaction which influenced the teachers’ teaching performance. Married teachers were more content than single teachers because they thought of their families who needed their support.

Problem 7: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents’ level of teaching competencies and the effectiveness of ALIVE implementation?

Table 23. Relationship Between the Respondent’s Level of Teaching Competencies and the Effectiveness of ALIVE Implementation

Teaching Competencies	Availability of School Facilities	Availability of Instructional Materials	Extent of Instructional Support	Total Measure
Knowledge	0.014 ^{ns} (0.934)	0.206 ^{ns} (0.215)	0.170 ^{ns} (0.308)	0.192 ^{ns} (0.247)
Attitude	-0.113 ^{ns} (0.497)	0.024 ^{ns} (0.886)	0.065 ^{ns} (0.697)	-0.023 ^{ns} (0.889)
Skills	0.192 ^{ns} (0.248)	0.180 ^{ns} (0.280)	-0.207 ^{ns} (0.212)	0.123 ^{ns} (0.461)
Total Measure	0.049 ^{ns} (0.769)	0.229 ^{ns} (0.167)	0.028 ^{ns} (0.867)	0.167 ^{ns} (0.316)

Note: Values expressed in r-value (P-value) ns-not significant at 0.05 level (P-value > 0.05)

Table 23 presents the relationship between the respondents’ level of teaching competencies and the effectiveness of ALIVE implementation using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. The result showed that the respondent’s level of teaching competencies was not significantly associated with the effectiveness of ALIVE implementation since the observed p-values exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. Further, the knowledge, attitude, and skills teaching competencies of the teachers were not related to effectiveness of ALIVE implementation relative to the availability of school facilities, instructional materials, and extent of instructional support. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the respondents’ level of teaching competencies and the effectiveness of ALIVE implementation was not rejected.

The results implied that there were other factors that affected the teaching competencies of the ALIVE teachers, not just limited to the availability of school facilities, instructional materials, and extent of instructional support. According to Jamaluddin and Cadir (2017), due to the insecurities of the Asatidz, they tried to seek more training and preparations to become highly specialized in the Arabic language.

Problem 8: Is there a significant relationship between the socio-and annual teaching performance of the Asatidz?

Table 24 presents the relationship between the respondents’ sociodemographic file and their annual teaching performance using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. The result displayed that the Sociodemographic file by the respondents was not significantly associated with their teaching performance ($r=-0.001, p=0.05$). In addition, the socio-demographic file level relative to Age ($r=0.155, p=0.352$), civil status ($r=0.316, p=0.53$), secular education ($r=-0.103, p=0.540$), and Madrash Education ($r=0.227, p=0.171$) Eligibility ($r=-0.081, p=0.628$) Years of service ($r=-0.446, p=0.005$) seminar attended ($r=-0.307, p=0.061$) Salary ($r=-0.179, p=0.284$) were not significantly correlated to their teaching performance.

This result entailed that the teaching performance of the respondents was not linearly associated with their socio-demographic file. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the sociodemographic file and the teaching performance of the respondents was not rejected.

Table 24. Relationship between the Socio-Demographic and Annual Teaching Performance of the Asatidz

Profile	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Age	0.155	0.352	Not significant
Sex (Female)	-0.093	0.579	Not significant
Civil Status			
Single	-0.225	0.174	Not significant
Married	0.316	0.053	Not significant
Widow	-0.199	0.231	Not significant
Secular Education			
Elementary	0.103	0.540	Not significant
High School	-0.192	0.247	Not significant
Undergraduate	0.055	0.744	Not significant
Madrassa Education			
High School	-0.024	0.886	Not significant
Undergraduate	-0.143	0.393	Not significant
Graduate	0.227	0.171	Not significant
Eligibility (QEALIS)	-0.081	0.628	Not significant
Appointment Status (Contractual)	-0.115	0.492	Not significant
Years of Service			
1-5	0.217	0.190	Not significant
6-10	-0.446**	0.005	Significant
11-above	0.238	0.151	Not significant
Seminar Attended			
1-3	0.208	0.210	Not significant
4-5	-0.307	0.061	Not significant
above 5	0.036	0.831	Not significant
Salary (4000-5000)	-0.179	0.284	Not significant

Note: **.significant at 0.01 level not significant means p-value > 0.05

April Rose (2020) stated that teacher's demographic characteristics have been one of the most important considerations for developing educational system. However, the performance review is one of the essential elements in educational institution. Having such will create motivation among teachers and perform better their work.

Problem 9: What action plan can be formulated based on the output of the study?

The action plan in this study was based on the significant findings of the study that were deemed relevant to improve the implementation of the ALIVE program and the teaching efficiency of the Asatidz. The objectives of the action plan are to provide opportunities for the Asatidz to improve their skills and training in understanding the English materials, using ICT in the classroom, developing localized learning materials, and increasing their skills in classroom management.

Conclusion

It was evident that identifying the challenges experienced among ALIVE teachers and competencies was highly important in determining the effectiveness of the ALIVE program implementation. It could be concluded that teachers were equipped with competencies in skills, attitude, and knowledge of the Arabic language. However, they encountered challenges in terms of delayed honorarium, insufficient salaries or allowances provided by the government, lack of supervision from DepEd, lack of classroom supplies and instructional materials in teaching ALIVE and lack of trainings and seminars in teaching ALIVE.

Consequently, it was also evident that though limited, they were provided with learning materials to use in their teaching. Furthermore, it was concluded that there were other factors that affected the teaching competencies of the ALIVE teachers, not just limited to the availability of school facilities, instructional materials, and extent of instructional support. Further, teachers' level of teaching competencies was significantly associated with their civil status.

Teachers should be provided with regular salary/honorariums, financial assistance in activities, and training on developing instructional materials. (1) Learners should be provided with localized and contextualized developed IMs and other instructional materials for the ALIVE curriculum to make them appreciate more the Arabic language not written in English. (2) School administrators should provide development of monitoring and evaluation instruments for ALIVE curriculum, seek financial assistance for professional development of Asatidz, and seek for Infrastructure projects for ALIVE learners and Asatidz. (3) DepEd should support the requests of school heads regarding the needs of their Asatidz. (4) Future researchers should find more ways to deal with the different challenges of ALIVE teachers and their needs to improve their instruction.

References

Arsad, N. (2007). A framework for integration of madrasah into the basic education curriculum. A Masteral Thesis, College of Education, University of the Philippines, Diliman.

- Ali, J. S. (2013). Level of competencies of arabic teachers in the district of Balindong. A Master's Thesis Presented to the Faculty of the Graduate School Mindanao State University: file:///C:/Users/DepED/Downloads/200141101104723-conversion-gate02.pdf.
- Biyani, A.A., Bagheri H., Bayani A. (2013). Influence of gender, age, and years of teaching experience on Burnout. *Annals of Biological Research*, 2013 4.
- Bodhe C.D., & Jankar D. S. (2015). Teaching effectiveness: How do students evaluate them teacher? *International J. of healthcare and Biomedical Research*, Volume 63, Issue: 02, January 2015. Pp. 155-159.
- Boransing, M. (2006). Road map to Muslim basic education. Diliman: University of the Philippines. Department of Education. (2004, August 28). [deped.gov.ph: https://www.deped.gov.ph/2004/08/28/do-51-s-2004-standardscurriculum-for-elementary-public-schools-and-private-madaris-amendedby-do-40-s-2011-amendment-to-deped-order-no-51-s-2004-standardcurriculum-for-elementary-public/](https://www.deped.gov.ph/2004/08/28/do-51-s-2004-standardscurriculum-for-elementary-public-schools-and-private-madaris-amendedby-do-40-s-2011-amendment-to-deped-order-no-51-s-2004-standardcurriculum-for-elementary-public/).
- DepEd Order 41, s. 2. (2017, August 11). Policy guidelines on MADRASAH education in the K to 12 basic education program. Manila, Philippines. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wpcontent/uploads/2017/08/DO_s2017_41.pdf.
- DepEd Order No. 51, s. 2. (2004, August 28). Standards curriculum for elementary public schools and private madaris. Amended By Do 40, S. 2011 – Amendment To Deped Order No. 51, S. 2004 (Standard Curriculum For Elementary Public Schools And Private Madaris). Manila, Philippines. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2004/08/28/do-51-s-2004>.
- Deporos, S. R. (2015). A comparative study of weekend developmental madrasah curriculum in Davao City, Philippines. *Research Journal*.
- Flamiano, A. (2015). ALIVE program national public school holiday. (Interview on 7th of September in al-Maarif Islamic School in Bokawkan Road, Baguio City).
- Figuroa, L., Lim, S., & Lee, J. (2016). Investigating the relationship between school facilities and academic achievements through geographically weighted regression. *Annals of GIS*, 22(4), 273-285.
- Frye, A. W. (2013). Program evaluation models and related theories. C. Dick, <https://jcesom.marshall.edu/media/53474/program-evaluation-models-and-related-theories.pdf>
- Godoy, F., & Astudilla, N. (2008). Arabic language and Islamic values education (ALIVE) program. Cordillera Administrative Region: Department of Education.
- Hamsira A. Harad & Benjier H. Arriola (2022). Challenges on the implementation of Arabic language and Islamic values education (ALIVE) program. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*, Volume 4, Issue 9, pp. 17-26, 2022.
- Hew, K. F., & Brush, T. (2007). Integrating technology into K-12 teaching and learning: Current knowledge gaps and recommendations for future research. *Education Tec Research Dev*, 2nd, 223–252. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-006-9022-5>
- Jamaluddin, A., & Cadir, B., (2017). Madrasah education in Zamboanga City as foundation of the Muslim way of life. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319456235>.
- Jamaluddin, A. & B. T. Cadir (2017). Madrasah education in Zamboanga City as the foundation of the Muslim way of life for peaceful, responsible, and productive citizen: Basis for 5-year strategic development plan. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation at Universidad de Zamboanga, Zamboanga City for the Degree Doctor of Education (Ed.D.), 2017
- Jaminal, B. (2019). The impact of school facilities to the teaching and learning environment. *SMCC Higher Educational Journal*. 12, 42– 54.
- Johnson, L., Becker, S., Cummins, M., Estrada, V., Freeman, A., & Hall, C. (2016). NMC new horizon report: 2016 higher education edition (pp. 1-150). The new media consortium.
- Kawangit, R., Aini, Z., & Marlon, Y. (2015). Impact of the Implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic values education (ALIVE) program in the Philippines. *Educational Research Journal*, 2015; Vol. 2 (27-32)
- Lamla, M. (2018). Issues and concerns on Madrasah education in Basilan, Philippines: The Asaatiz perspectives. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning* Vol. 5, Issue 4, pp: (1-4).
- Lewallen, T. (2016). The whole school, the whole community, the whole child model: A new approach for improving educational attainment and healthy development for students. *Journal of School Health*, 85 (11), 729-739
- Marasigan, A.C. (2019). Sustainability concerns of the madrasah education : Basis for Philippine Islamic and madrasah education

policy review. UP CIDS Discussion Paper 2019-10, 2019.

Mart, C. T. (2011). How to sustain students' motivation in a learning environment. Online Submission. Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies.

Maruhom, M. M. (2012). Readiness and competencies of Arabic language and

Islamic values education (ALIVE) teachers in the Non-Muslim and Muslim regions in Mindanao: Basis for policy making. Mindanao State University, Marawi City.

McKinsey. (2007). McKinsey 2007 Report. Kansas. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/social-sector/our-insights/how-the-worlds-best-performing-school-systems-come-out-on-top>.

Odanga S. J., Aloka P. J., & Raburu P. (2015). Influence of marital status on teachers' self-efficacy in secondary schools of Kisumu County, Kenya. Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies.

Omoifo, E. D. E. & Okaka, R. O. (2010). Imperatives of effective instructional delivery in physical education in secondary schools. Studies in education, Vol. 11, 48 – 64.

Ponders, V.E. (2011). The influence of teachers' biographic attributes and preparation on student achievement in public funds Detroit school (Electronic version). Dissertation Abstract International, vol. 84, 62-70.

Raths, L. E. (1978). Values and Teaching. Sage Journals, 275. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/019263656605031246>

Shah, S., & Udgaonkar, U. (2018). Influence of gender, civil status and age of teachers on teaching: Students' perspective. International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences. ISSN: 2319-7706 Volume 7 Number 01 (2018).

Sannad, J. (2015). ALIVE program. (Interview on 9th of September in Department of Education Cordillera Administrative Region, Benguet).

Saeli, M., Perrenet, J., Jochems, W. M. G., & Zwaneveld, B. (2012). Programming: Teachers and Pedagogical Content Knowledge in the Netherlands. Informatics in Education, 11(1), 81–114.

Selvi, K. (2010). Teachers' Competencies. International Journal of Philosophy of Culture and Axiology, 7(1), 167–176.

Slavin, R. E. (2006). Educational psychology: Theory and practice (8th ed.). (A. E. Burvikovs, Ed.) USA: Library of Congress Cataloging-in-Publication Data. file:///C:/Users/DepED/Downloads/Main%20Reference_Educ%20P.

Solaiman, S. (2017). Implementation of Arabic language and Islamic values education (ALIVE) in Marawi City, Philippines: Unveiling the perceptions of ALIVE teachers. Education Journal, 2017; 6(1): 38-46, 10.11648/j.edu.20170601.

Subroto, W. (2013). Income and implications of teacher performance to improve the quality of education in the elementary school of Surabaya. International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology Vol. 3 No. 2; February 2013.

Zamel, M. A. (2017). Ibn-Khaldun's concept of education: Pre-conditions and quality. British Journal of Education, Volume 5(4), 95-106. <http://www.eajournals.org/wp-content/uploads/IBN%E2%80%Concept-ofEducation-Pre-Conditions.pdf>.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Norhanifa P. Asum

Darimbang Elementary School
Department of Education – Philippines

Carlito A. Abarquez, PhD

St. Peter's College – Philippines